

A customizable, multi-parametric auditory display technique for theta-alpha neurofeedback training

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Abstract

Advances in physiological measurement systems allowed equipment that used to be exclusive to medical or research centers to be acquired and used by virtually anyone. The Electroencephalogram is a good example of how these new technologies are getting closer to the non-scientific community, with portable and affordable devices like the Enobio and the Emotiv EPOC brain-computer interfaces. Together with advances in fields like behavioral and cognitive neurosciences, and psychology, we now can easily access complex data that gives us unparalleled insight of our brain and body states. On the other hand, the field of Auditory Display is a relatively young one but has nonetheless been successfully applied to a great group of very diverse research fields (data exploration, musical composition, interaction design, and for studying medical conditions to cite a few). Being perfectly suitable for displaying complex physiological data, it has been gaining much attention in last decades, especially when applied to monitoring and biofeedback systems. One important issue that arises from this situation is the fact that in such an interdisciplinary field, sonification experts have to design mappings for many different situations and users.

In this master thesis we aim at investigating how the use of multi-parameterization combined with the user customization of such mappings can play a role in the field of auditory neurofeedback. In order to explore this problem we developed a system capable of generating a broad range of sonifications from EEG signals and used it to explore these concepts in the well-established Theta-Alpha Neurofeedback Training paradigm. We analyze the subjective and physiological response from the subjects in an experimental scenario involving customizable natural soundscapes and musical elements as an auditory display of brain activity in specific frequency bands.

Results show that multi-parameterization seem to have a positive influence in the neurofeedback scenario and can be a promising direction to pursue while user-customization is desired but still require some improvements to become feasible.

KEYWORDS: Electroencephalography, EEG, Sonification, Auditory display, Biofeedback, Neurofeedback, Sound perception, Psychoacoustics, alpha band, theta band, theta alpha ratio, music

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1. Introduction

1.1 – Context

With the advances of physiological measurement techniques like the electroencephalography, paralleled with research in fields as cognitive and behavioral neuroscience and psychology, it is now possible to measure and classify neural correlates of different cognitive and affective states by analyzing specific EEG features [1]. It's also important to notice how these devices are increasingly small, portable and affordable. That means that this technology is now available for the regular user and not only something exclusive of hospitals, clinics and research centers. Data acquired by equipment like the EEG is very complex and multi-dimensional in nature. In order to present it to the user, some relevant decisions have to be taken. Such information can be displayed using visualization techniques and/or sonification strategies, either with pre-recorded data or in real time. The later is used for two main purposes: state monitoring or neurofeedback.

1.2 - Problem Statement

The neurofeedback paradigm is a type of biofeedback that displays the users' brain activity in real time, with signals acquired either from an EEG, PET or fMRI system. Due to its higher time-resolution, the EEG is usually the choice. Many neurofeedback applications require the use of the subject's visual channel for specific tasks or can't use it at all when the task itself requires eyes to be closed (e.g. when trying to induce sleep or states of deep relaxation). In these situations the auditory counterpart becomes even more important. When displaying EEG activity by means of sonification, one crucial aspect is the mapping from EEG-to-Sound. The low frequency range of EEG activity is not suitable for direct amplification, and thus at least some transformation on the data is required for a human listener to be able to perceive the sound. This mapping can be quite arbitrary and being so, the following duality arises:

- A direct and reversible mapping can preserve all the information contained in the original signal but is unnatural and hard to perceptually decode (e.g. in "audification", the original temporal data is kept as it is and usually just frequency shifted so it can be presented within the range of an audible sound).
- When applying more complex mappings, the perceptual quality of the resulting sound can be greatly improved but information from the original signal is lost, since some kind of irreversible transformation usually has to be applied (e.g.

musical mappings, where some EEG features are converted to musical features of a computer-generated piece).

Also, typically only one (or some) dimension(s) of the data being explored are of interest for a given application and when that's the case, only these specific features have to be translated to the auditory and/or visual domain. With that in mind, two possible ways of reducing the effects of the issue exposed above are proposed:

A - The system designer may allow the final user to fine tune his or her own mappings. Ideally a subject should be able to design her own mapping in order to focus on the specific features required and their own subjective liking. As an example, a musician would probably perform better detecting smooth nuances of the sonified data in a carefully tailored musical mapping than in an arbitrary sonification that uses any sort of sounds. On the other hand, a mechanical would probably be very used to extract information from slight changes of a car's engine sound and this could his optimum mapping (an engine sound model). It should be clear that designing a universal mapping that suits any auditory neurofeedback scenario is an extremely hard (if not impossible) task. By giving some control to the user, we aim at reducing the subjectivity inherent to the mapping design, or at least transferring these decisions to the subject himself. It is important to notice that most of the current sonification techniques applied to EEG data only offer pre-defined, fixed mappings.

B – When treating multivariate, multidimensional complex data as a human EEG signal, one single state can correlate to many different features. The number of signal dimensions that should be used to generate a neurofeedback auditory display is crucial and subject to perceptual limitations. By increasing the number of signal dimensions (coherent and sometimes even redundant EEG features to be sonified) we get a more robust but also more complex display. Here again we deal with a trade-off between information bandwidth and easiness of perceptual decoding. One proposed solution is to increase the number of features to be mapped into sound elements (or its parameters) but having them varying in consonance with each other so that the subject can correlate the desired state into a single perceptual quality of the resulting sound environment.

In the following chapters we present the State-of-the-Art of the field, the system we have designed to explore our research questions, the methods and experimental setup used, our results and discussion.

2. State-of-the-art

In the following sections, an overview of concepts and previous research related to this thesis is presented. Neuroanatomy, EEG and DSP concepts are discussed in a basic level, followed by a historical overview on auditory displays and a more exhaustive discussion over EEG sonification techniques developed in the last couple decades. Special emphasis is given to the neurofeedback paradigm.

2.1 – The anatomy of the Human Brain

The human central nervous system is composed of the cerebrum, the cerebellum and the medulla oblongata (or brain stem). The research presented in this document concerns the cerebrum and analysis of its electrical activity. Figure 1 presents the four lobes of the left hemisphere of the human brain.

Figure 1: The four lobes of the human brain – Gray's Anatomy

The largest of them is the frontal lobe, situated at the anterior tip of the brain and extended to the central sulcus, which separates it from the temporal lobe. It is know to

be responsible for the primary motor functions as well as what are called executive functions: personality, insight and foresight [2].

The parietal lobe, located in the central part of the brain, is generally associated with three main functions:

- Initial cortical processing of positional and tactile information;
- Spatial orientation and directing attention;
- Language comprehension;

The temporal lobe is in charge of high-order processing of visual information and auditory information, playing an important role in learning and memory.

Finally, the smallest of the four, the occipital lobe can be found in the rear of the skull, and is almost exclusively associated with visual functions.

2.2 – Electroencephalography, EEG Rhythms and Signal Processing

Electroencephalography is a technique for measuring brain electrical activity presented in 1912 by the Russian physiologist Vladimir Vladimirovich Pravdich-Neminsky [3]. Hans Berger, who is also credited for the invention of the electroencephalogram, first used it with humans in 1924. [4]

It refers to recording electrical activity within the cerebral cortex by attaching electrodes to a person's scalp. These electrodes are sensitive to very small voltage fluctuations resulting from ionic current flows within the brain's neurons being measured. For higher voltage readings the electrodes could be placed directly on the surface of the brain, but that demands an invasive surgical procedure that is clearly not suitable for many types of research.

Electrical activity measured by EEG is known to be oscillatory in nature since it's first recording by Dr. Berger. It is usually classified according to its spectral content and divided into different frequency bands as shown in figure 2. There's no agreed range for each frequency band but the most used grouping goes as follows:

- Delta: 0.5 to 4 Hz
- Theta: 4 to 8 Hz
- Alfa: 8 to 13 Hz
- Beta: 14 to 30 Hz
- Gamma: 30 a >100 Hz

Figure 2 – The EEG Frequency bands

Modern EEG equipment can be compact, lightweight and low-cost. These devices usually have an integrated amplifier and analog-to-digital converter, allowing the acquired signal to be fed into a personal computer for further processing and analysis. With the aid of techniques like digital filtering and envelope detection, we are able to obtain the energy concentrated in each of these bands and their cognitive correlate.

The full signal bandwidth ranges from 0.5 Hz to 30-40 Hz. Classification of EEG signals is made based on frequency, and historically, five types of rhythmic activity have been used: alpha (α), beta (β), theta (θ), delta (δ) and gamma (γ). There is no precise agreement on the frequency range for each type. The following paragraphs describe briefly each of the bands and the activity they are associated with.

Delta Rhythms - Usually up to 4 Hz, these are waves of high amplitude and are picked up from the frontal cortex in adults and posteriorly in children. The state is usually that of slow wave sleep in adults, although they are detected during some continuous attention tasks as well.

Theta Rhythms - Between 4-8 Hz normally, these rhythms are detected in locations not related to the task at hand. They are frequently observed in young children, during phases of drowsiness or arousal and idling.

Alpha Rhythms - of particular relevance to this study, alpha rhythms oscillate at approximately 7-13 Hz and are found on either side of the posterior regions of the head. They are higher in amplitude on the non-dominant side. The central sites (C3-C4) are at rest. Alpha waves are particularly prominent in subjects who are relaxed and awake with their eyes closed, alpha suppression takes place in open-eye conditions.

Beta Rhythms – These are fast rhythms oscillating between 14-30 Hz. The amplitudes are relatively low. Beta rhythms are associated with an activated cortex and can be observed during certain sleep stages. The main points of observation are the frontal and central regions of the scalp.

Gamma Rhythms – Gamma rhythms are fast rhythms oscillating above 30 Hz indicative of a state of active information processing in the cortex [5].

2.3 – Auditory Displays and EEG Sonification Techniques

Auditory displays are techniques for presenting information in the auditory domain. It is a field concerned with the study of how the human auditory system can be used as the primary interface channel for communicating and transmitting information. It encompasses all the aspects of the system, the setup, speakers/headphones, modes of interaction within the display and all the processing and computing required to obtain a conversion from data to sound. Sonification is one of its main components, being “the technique of rendering sound in response to data and interactions” [6].

2.3.1 – EEG Sonification: An overview

Recent developments in wearable computing and wireless low- cost physiological sensors have brought brain activity monitoring out of the lab. Many such systems are now commercially available (e.g. NeuroSky [7], Enobio [8], Emotiv [9] and Nexus [10]).

Progress in these areas has been accompanied by equally rapid developments in auditory hardware, signal processing techniques and wearable audio capability. These joint developments make practical several new approaches for exploiting the real-time representation of brain activity using sound. The sonification opportunities created in this way promise new applications in several areas; pervasive medicine and health monitoring, neuro and biofeedback and implicit interaction interfaces, as well as in other domains that involve the real-time sensing of users perceptual, emotional and cognitive states. Sound-based monitoring and feedback of physiological data have clear

advantages in these areas. Indeed, in many respects human auditory perception provides the highest temporal resolution among the sensory modalities. Additionally, in many cases the non-visual information channel is more suitable for wearable applications.

The idea of making electroencephalographic (EEG) signals audible accompanied brain imaging development from the very first steps in the early 1930s. For example, Prof. Edgar Adrian listened to his own EEG signal while replicating Hans Bergers experiments [4]. Indeed, sonification appears to be well suited for applications based on real-time EEG, since sound can readily represent the complexity and fast temporal dynamics of brain signals. Since the 1930s, a number of scholars and media artists have been experimenting with converting EEG activity into sound. Unfortunately, many of these studies have used rather arbitrary data-to-sound conversions. In addition, the associated publications often do not provide sufficient details about either physiological data acquisition or applied sound synthesis. Very few of these studies have conducted any kind of controlled evaluation of their chosen methods, making it impossible to replicate or validate most studies. Given these widespread limitations, a critical review of the current state of this emerging multidisciplinary field may facilitate its future healthy development.

2.3.2 – Application areas of EEG Sonification

In the next chapters, the outcome of an analysis of more than fifty real-time EEG sonification works is presented. They are classified by the techniques employed to generate sound and the EEG features used.

Two main applications of real-time EEG sonification have to be distinguished: monitoring and neurofeedback. *Real-time monitoring* is designed to inform a third person about the user's state (e.g. an anesthetist during surgery [12]) or informing the user of his/her own state (e.g. a pilot or driver being warned of his critical fatigue level). *Neurofeedback* applications target learning about a users own brain state and, importantly, aim at altering this state, e.g. for post-stroke rehabilitation. Figure 3 divides the various types of EEG sonification in a 2-dimensional map.

Figure 3 - Bi-dimensional map of EEG sonification application areas [21]

These application domains have different goals, different constraints and different validation methods. One of the dimensions that helps to differentiate between all the sonification approaches is to contrast ways in which one would expect the end results to be judged, for example quantitative vs. qualitative judgment. With Miranda's BCMI [13], just listening to the sonification may be sufficient for demonstrating that the system works. With BCI based musical instruments like in [14], the player can judge the extent to which the interface allows the musically necessary degree of control. But both of these domains are more concerned with the aesthetics of the resulting sonic composition than any other kind of validation. The situation is very different for diagnostic and neurofeedback uses of real-time EEG sonification, where the informational and perceptual value of produced sounds is of primary importance and determines the functionality of the application.

3. System Design

In this chapter the whole system will be described in detail. The session is composed of three main parts: The general considerations, the data-acquisition and DSP system and finally the sonification engine designed with its strategies and mappings.

3.1 – General Considerations

For designing a system for real-time auditory neurofeedback many technical constraints have to be satisfied. The diagram in Figure 4 represents the system developed and used for this project. It is grouped in three main modules responsible for 1- acquiring the signal, 2- extracting the desired EEG features, and 3- generating the sound output.

Figure 4 - The EEG-to-sound chain

Since our research deals with real-time sonification, it was utterly important to maintain a constant data flow through the entire signal chain. This has to be done within the boundaries imposed by the acceptable delay that arises from real time signal processing. Using previous research as a reference, we established a limit of 3000 milliseconds delay between an onset on the EEG side of the chain to its sonic response [15].

3.2 – Data acquisition and DSP

The Emotiv EPOC wireless neuroheadset [9] was selected for signal acquisition due to its low cost and good temporal resolution. Data acquired with it is converted to a digital signal at a sampling rate of 128Hz. Using the Emotiv EPOC Research SDK we have access to the raw data that is then fed into a Matlab/Simulink [16] model for further processing.

This model can be customized for each desired neurofeedback and/or monitoring application created. To achieve this goal, a toolbox (Figure 6) was developed, allowing us to obtain and process a great number of EEG features. The OSC block allows direct communication via UDP with virtually any modern real-time sound synthesis environment through the Open Sound Control protocol [17].

Figure 6: The Matlab/Simulink EEG Toolbox

The toolbox will also comprises some visualization blocks that allows the final user to have insight about the spatial origin of the neuronal activity by using positional inference based on the *LORETA* (low-resolution brain electromagnetic tomography) technique [18].

3.3 – Sonification Engine

In this section, the various mappings are described in their direct form. The system is intended to allow the control over these mappings so that any relationship between data and sonification parameter can be inverted or even canceled. The description below corresponds to the direct, default parameterization (referred to as “fixed mapping” from now on).

3.3.1 - Pedal:

A fixed pitch tonic is initialized on loading (“D2”, midi note n°38) and a tremolo effect is applied and phase shifted to each of the even harmonics, giving a slowly moving chorus-like timbre to the drone.

- Tremolo is linearly mapped to the control signal
- Panning is linearly mapped to the control signal
- Gain is linearly mapped to the control signal

Figure 7: The Pedal

3.3.2 - Melody:

Melody is constructed using a major scale spanning from five semitones (one fourth) below the central tonic to sixteen semitones above it (major third).

Figure 8: The main melody

- Note triggering speed is a function of the slope of the signal (in direct mapping, faster changes yield more notes per second)
- Note pitch is controlled by the slope (rate of change) of the incoming signal. In direct mapping, positive changes yield ascending pitch while negative ones lead melody downwards. Higher rate of change yields bigger jumps in melody (more semitones between two consecutive notes)
- Note volume is a linear function of the input signal

3.3.3 - Soundscape rewards

One block of the engine is devoted to enhancing the foreground elements of the generated soundscape by triggering specific sound effects (nature sounds like birds, owls, crickets, etc.) when the control signal goes over 50% of the calibrated maximum value. In this sense, every time the subject's Theta/Alpha ratio is over this predefined threshold he/she is "rewarded" with a more vivid yet still relaxing soundscape.

Figure 9 - Sonic rewards

There're no parameters mapped to this part of the engine besides the triggering itself being a function of the power of the control signal. Dynamic panning allows the perception of an immersive three-dimensional environment.

3.3.4 – Windy sound-scape

A procedural audio approach was chosen for this block of the sonification engine. A series of white noise generators are filtered and modulated in different frequency bands and with different delays to generate a sound scape environment that resembles a windy scenario. The idea of using procedural audio (in contrast to a sample-based approach) was to give complete control of the sound parameters to the designer. Different features can be plugged to different parameters allowing a mapping that changes the perceptual quality of the windy scene according to the select data features.

The mapping used for the experiments uses the incoming signal to control wind speed of the modeled sound object. In direct mapping, the higher the input the faster the wind will blow.

Figure 10 - Wind sound synth

3.3.5 – Rainy sound-scape

For this block we decided to use a sample based approach aiming at the fidelity of the resulting sound and also to allow a comparison with the pros and cons of the procedural audio approach of the “wind” block. Dynamic cross fading between different rain recordings was used to modulate the sound. Input signal modulates the amount of each of the samples in the resulting sound that goes from light rain to a small thunderstorm. Only one parameter is used in the final patch, varying linearly and controlling the “Rain density” perceptual quality.

3.3.6 – The control module

Another Pd abstraction was created to allow the patching between all the previous mentioned blocks and the data communication one. It contains time and frequency signal monitoring scopes for both input and output data. This control module is also responsible for the midi communication between the system and the user. A subject is able to adjust his/her mapping on the fly with a standard midi controller, listening to the results as the neurofeedback or monitoring process is going.

Figure 11 - Sample-based rain generator

Figure 12: The control block

The user is allowed to customize / fine-tune the mappings as follows. One data feature is associated to one sound element (e.g. alpha band power is mapped to the amount of rain). The user is allowed to change how this mapping is done in a continuous scale from -1 to +1. If the potentiometer is dragged to -1, the mapping is inverted, i.e. a greater value of the data feature yields a smaller value for the sound parameter (more alpha would lead to less rain). If it is positioned at 1, the mapping is positive (more alpha yields more rain). In the middle (zero), the sound is fixed and not influenced by the data (in this example, there would be a fixed amount of rain equivalent to 50% of its maximum value, independently of the alpha power).

In Figure 12 we can see an example configuration within the block “User_controlled_parameters” where the Rain and Wind models are fixed at 50% and the Theta/Alpha ratio is directly mapped to the Foreground sound engine (Pedal + Melody + Soundscape rewards).

4. Methods

4.1 – Research Question

The research presented here is concerned with answering the following questions:

A- Do personalized, custom EEG sonification mappings perform better than predefined, fixed ones in a T/A Neurofeedback scenario?

B- Is it possible to improve the identification of a cognitive state and its sonified EEG correlate by increasing the number of features mapped to the Auditory Display in a T/A Neurofeedback scenario?

Concerning the number of features used for generating the sonification, we hypothesize that a multiple-feature mapping will be perceived as more relaxing and more representative of the subject's relaxation state. This should be noticeable by both the subjective and objective measurements acquired during the experiments.

The rhythmic structure of brain signals is very complex and the link between the activity in each frequency band for each region of the brain and its cognitive correlates are still not completely understood. The use of more than one feature to represent a certain mental state is desirable in the sense that it should allow a more robust and complete representation of the complex patterns that arise from the analysis of the EEG signal.

We also hypothesize that a user-customizable mapping should have a better performance than a pre-defined, fixed one. The higher familiarity of a subject with a mapping fine-tuned by himself as well as the possibility of adjusting it to his liking should yield better results in terms of neurofeedback and induced relaxation. As in the first hypothesis, this difference should be noticeable by both subjective and objective measurements acquired in the experimental scenario.

4.2 – Experimental Setup

To operationalize such questions, we developed an experiment using the Theta-Alpha (T/A) Neurofeedback Training paradigm, and the above-mentioned DSP and Sound Engine systems. The experiment aims at inducing a state of deep relaxation on the subjects and allowing some degree of control of how their EEG features are converted to sound. To allow us inquiring both research questions we created four groups of subjects as described in the next section.

4.3 – Sample and Groups

A total sample of twenty subjects with ages between 23 and 30, and equally distributed between men and women was distributed in the following groups:

Single feature, Fixed mapping (SF): Can't control the mapping between data and sound and only one EEG feature (the Theta/Alpha ratio) is used to control one element of the sound engine.

Multiple features, Fixed mappings (MF): Can't control the mapping between data and sound but three EEG features (Alpha, Theta and the Theta/Alpha ratio) are used to control three different elements of the sound engine.

Single Feature, Custom mapping (SC): Can tune the feature-to-sound mapping to their liking, only having one feature mapped to one sound element.

Multiple features, Custom mappings (MC): Can tune the feature-to-sound mapping to their liking, having three features mapped to three sound elements.

Each group is composed of five subjects and all of them go through the same steps as described in the next chapter.

From now on we will refer to these four groups by their respective codes: SF, MF, SC and MC.

4.4 - Experimental design

In this section we discuss the many aspects related to how the experiment was designed. The organization of the sampling groups and experimental procedure, physical setup of the equipment and data acquisition are discussed in detail.

4.4.1 – Experimental protocol

The experiment is comprised of three main steps:

- 1- Mapping adjustment;
- 2- Basal state inducing, with a pre-recorded relaxing sound scape;
- 3- Neurofeedback session;

Three subjective measurements of arousal and valence levels are done three times using the SAM Scale [19], [20]:

- 1- When the subject arrives at the lab;
- 2- After the 5-minute control session with pre-recorded relaxing sound scape;
- 3- After the neurofeedback session;

Figure 12 - Experimental setup

The setup is done with a quadraphonic system where the sound elements are positioned around the subject to give an immersive, realistic experience. The lights are dimmed down for the adjustment and pre-relaxation sessions and completely turned off for the neurofeedback session. Figure 12 shows one of our subjects preparing to begin the session.

Figure 13 – Experimental setup diagram

Figure 13 represents the setup used for the experiment. Great attention was given to avoid electromagnetic interference between the equipment. The subject’s positioning was also a topic of concern since he/she should always be at the “sweet spot” (the point in the room equally distant to the four loudspeakers, where the sound is correctly balanced).

The two computers used were of similar configuration:

DSP and Signal Acquisition Station: Intel Core2-Duo 2.0 GHz with 2GB RAM running Matlab R2012a and the Emotiv Eloc Signal Server on Windows 7.

Sound Engine Computer: Intel Core2-Duo 2.6GHz with 4GB RAM running PureData 0.42.5-Extended on MAC OSX 10.8.

4.4.2 – Measures

For the subsequent analysis, subjective and objective data was collect for every subject.

For acquiring the subjective data, a paper form was created using the standard 9-point SAM Scale as a tool for enquiring the subject’s mood. This is done in terms of arousal and valence. In Figure 14 the printed form scale can be seen.

Figure 14 - Subjective mood assessment: The SAM Scale

This form is presented three times during the experiment for each subject, who’s asked to mark a number from 1 to 9 that best represents his/her current state in terms of Valence and Arousal.

For the objective analysis, raw data acquired by the Emotiv EPOC was recorded using the Matlab / Simulink Toolbox prior to the DSP processing and later analyzed to extract the minima, the maxima and average value for alpha, theta and theta/alpha ratio in 3-minute blocks. The first and last 3-minute blocks were used in order to obtain a measurement of the evolution of each feature during the experiment.

5 – Results and analysis

5.1 – The dataset structure

As described previously, our subjects are divided in four groups according to the number of EEG features / Sound Parameters and the possibility of customizing or not the mapping scheme. Table 1 reviews and summarizes the nomenclature used for each group:

Code	Group name	N
SF	Single feature, fixed mapping	5
SC	Single feature, customizable mapping	5
MF	Multiple features, fixed mappings	5
MC	Multiple features, customizable mappings	5

Table 1 – Group description

In order to evaluate if the results are consistent with our hypotheses, we start comparing the subjective data acquired with the forms. The levels of arousal and valence as indicated by the subjects for each stage of the experiment are compared between the groups. Objective data acquired with the EEG system for each group is also compared using the Theta/Alpha ratio during the whole neurofeedback session.

5.2 – Subjective data (SAM scale)

In this section we describe the results regarding the data collected with the self-assessment of the subjects' levels of arousal and valence. First we compare the results for the paired groups (multiple vs. single-feature and custom vs. fixed mapping) and then for each one of the four.

5.2.1 – Multiple vs. Single-feature

Firstly we evaluate the significance of having multiple EEG features mapped to multiple parameters instead of a single one. The graph on Figure 15 shows the mean values for pre and post-neurofeedback session for each macro group. As expected, using multiple features seems to have a more effective result on decreasing the arousal levels of the subjects. An analysis of variance is performed with the Statistics Toolbox of Matlab and the resulting values of significance between pre and post-feedback session are presented for each group. The analysis of significance gives a positive result for the Multiple-feature group, with $p < 0.05$.

	Multiple Pre	Multiple Post	Single Pre	Single Post
Arousal Mean	3.4000	1.8000	2.5000	2.1000
Arousal Std.	1.5055	1.3166	1.9003	1.3703
P-value	0.0210		0.5959	
Valence Mean	4.7000	5.2000	6.5000	6.8000
Valence Std.	1.2517	2.0440	1.1785	1.6193
P-value	0.5178		0.6414	

Table 2 – SAM data grouped by number of features used

Figure 15 – SAM data analysis: Multiple vs. Single feature

5.2.2 – Custom vs. Fixed mappings

Now we combine the four groups into the macro-categories of custom and fixed mappings. The results can be seen in Figure 16. Here however it seems that the groups having fixed parameters perform better than the customizable ones. Running a 1-way analysis of variance we find that only the decrease in arousal of the fixed parameter group has a low p-value indicating some possible significance. Using a $p < 0.05$ threshold no variation can be evaluated as significant.

	Custom Pre	Custom Post	Fixed Pre	Fixed Post
Arousal Mean	1.9000	1.4000	4.0000	2.5000
Arousal Std.	0.9944	0.8433	1.6997	1.5092
P-Value	0.2409		0.0514	
Valence Mean	5.8000	5.7000	5.4000	6.3000
Valence Std.	1.5492	2.6687	1.5055	0.9487
P-Value	0.9195		0.1271	

Table 3 – SAM data grouped by mapping type (fixed vs. custom)

Figure 16 - Subjective analysis: Custom vs. Fixed mappings

5.2.3 – Analysis by groups

To further investigate the results presented in the previous sections, we go one level down and gather the individual results for each of the four groups. In Figure 17 the corresponding graph is presented.

Here we can see a trend for all groups when it comes to decreasing the arousal between pre and post-neurofeedback session. There also seems to be a trend to increase the valence between the two stages but with lower significance. The group with the smallest p-value (higher significance) is the one with multiple features and customizable mappings when it comes to reducing arousal. However, a p-value over 0.5 can't be considered to deny the null hypothesis (that the variation between before and after the session is enough to represent a statistical difference between then) and thus the results can't be considered significant.

Figure 17 - Subjective analysis: All four groups

	MC (pre)	MC (post)	MF (pre)	MF (post)
Valence (mean)	5.0000	4.6000	4.4000	5.8000
Valence (std)	1.2247	2.7928	1.3416	0.8367
P-Value	0.7768		0.0831	
Arousal (mean)	2.6000	1.6000	4.2000	2.0000
Arousal (std)	0.8944	0.5477	1.6432	1.8708
P-Value	0.0656		0.0836	

Table 4a – Descriptive statistics for the SAM data

	SC (pre)	SC (post)	SF (pre)	SF (post)
Valence (mean)	6.6000	6.8000	6.4000	6.8000
Valence (std)	1.5166	0.8367	0.8944	0.8367
P-Value	0.8743		0.4860	
Arousal (mean)	1.2000	1.2000	4.2000	2.0000
Arousal (std)	0.4472	1.0954	1.6432	1.8708
P-Value	1		0.4332	

Table 4b – Descriptive statistics for the SAM data

5.3 – EEG data: Objective measurements

In the following sections the results obtained with the analysis of the EEG data are presented. The Theta/Alpha ratio is the only feature used for all the subjects and it's also the most relevant one for Alpha-Theta Neurofeedback Training scenarios according to the bibliography.

5.3.1 – Multiple vs. single parameter

As with the subjective data, we start by comparing the results of the groups using multiple and single features before and after the neurofeedback session (stages 1 and 2 respectively)

Figure 18 – EEG data analysis: Multiple vs. Single feature

Time(s)	90	180	270	360	450	540	630	720	810	900
Multiple	0.623	0.543	0.683	0.657	0.720	0.824	0.912	0.974	1.050	0.947
Single	0.367	0.487	0.503	0.506	0.601	0.607	0.649	0.790	0.677	0.695

To investigate how significant these results are we perform an ANOVA contrasting the first and last 90s windows for each group. The results are that the significance falls short to the $p < 0.05$ criteria even though the difference between stages in the Multiple-feature group is bigger than in the Single-feature one.

ANOVA	Multiple feature	Single feature
P-Value	0.12	0.15

5.3.2 – Custom vs. fixed mappings

Figure 19 – EEG data analysis: Custom vs. Fixed Mappings

Time(s)	90	180	270	360	450	540	630	720	810	900
Custom	0.488	0.518	0.684	0.584	0.720	0.755	0.879	0.953	0.975	0.929
Fixed	0.504	0.511	0.482	0.578	0.588	0.668	0.660	0.814	0.728	0.689

ANOVA	Custom mappings	Fixed mappings
P-Value	0.10	0.17

5.3.3 – Individual groups

Here we gather the results for all the individual groups. Figure 20 shows the evolution in time for the theta/alpha ratio for each one of them. The lines represent the mean ratio of all subjects from each group. It has been calculated every 90 seconds during the neurofeedback sessions to get some insight on the evolution of this feature during the whole process.

All groups show a trend of increasing the T/A ratio during the neurofeedback session, which is a good indication that the procedure works even with just a 15-minute session. The MC group has the best results with a steeper curve and a final value much higher

than the others. The possible implications of this result are going to be analyzed in depth in the discussion session.

Figure 20 – EEG data analysis: Comparing all four groups

Group	90s	180s	270s	360s	450s	540s	630s	720s	810s	900s
MC	0.717	0.662	0.949	0.739	0.879	0.964	1.143	1.189	1.353	1.228
MF	0.529	0.424	0.418	0.575	0.560	0.685	0.680	0.759	0.747	0.666
SC	0.297	0.398	0.463	0.456	0.586	0.580	0.658	0.716	0.660	0.680
SF	0.428	0.587	0.526	0.545	0.580	0.618	0.602	0.891	0.661	0.677

Table 7 – TA ratio evolution in time (90s slots)

Now we present some basic statistical analysis to compare the first and last 90s blocks of each group. This is done in order to evaluate if there’s a significant increase in the ratio for every group and if it is more significant in some groups than others. The p-value was again calculated using the anova1 function of Matlab’s Statistics Toolbox.

Group	T3		T15		P value
	Mean	Std.	Mean	Std.	
MC	0.690	0.720	1.290	0.648	0.203
MF	0.477	0.393	0.707	0.401	0.386
SC	0.347	0.462	0.670	0.515	0.279
SF	0.507	0.164	0.669	0.174	0.207

Table 8 – First 3m vs. last 3m

In table 8 the mean values of ratio for the first and last 3 minutes of each group are presented. In the P-value column we compute the ANOVA for each group between the two time slots.

Despite the positive trend in favor of our approach, the analysis of variance can’t guarantee these values are significant. This will be further discussed in the next chapter.

6 - Discussion

6.1 – Multiple vs. Single feature

The first question we approach in this work is that about the number of EEG features used to generate a sound that conveys a subject's physiological state. As previously described, we create two scenarios to understand how this design decision plays a part in the overall system. The group using the Single-feature scheme only listens to a sonification of their Theta/Alpha ratio while the Multiple-feature group has one sound element mapped to each of the three brain signals acquires (Theta power, Alpha power and T/A ratio).

To enquire the relevance of using more features we analyze the subjective data acquired with the SAM scale form and the objective data measured by the EEG. As shown in sections 5.2.1 and 5.3.1 respectively, the multiple-feature group seems to perform better than the single-feature group in both scenarios. Even though the significance is low, the fact that both subjective and objective data point to the same direction is a very good indication that this approach should be further investigated and may result in improved performance for auditory neurofeedback scenarios.

6.2 – Custom vs. Fixed Mappings

The second question explored in this thesis is that of the advantage of having user-customizable mappings when using auditory displays in a neurofeedback scenario. Again we split the groups into two categories. The fixed mappings group is given a defined sonification strategy for each of the EEG features acquires while the custom mapping group's subjects have the chance of adjusting the mapping themselves. This proved to have advantages and disadvantages. On one hand, the customizable mappings allow the subject to achieve a more pleasant sound for his/her liking and also seem to facilitate the understanding of how the system works. On the other hand, many subjects have trouble trying to grasp how the system responded to their relaxation state while when the mapping was fixed it seemed easier for them to do such a task.

The data also points to different assumptions when comparing subjective and objective results. The SAM-scale analysis indicate that the users respond better to fixed mappings while the objective EEG data indicates a better result for the customizable mappings. The low significance of both results and the fact that they indicate opposite results let us believe that this question deserves further investigation and no conclusion should be extracted from this data. A bigger sample group and different experimental design are to be discussed in the "Future Work" session of this document as a means to further investigate the topic.

7 – Future Work and Conclusions

7.1 – Future Work

During the course of the evaluation we detected some challenges and speculated about possible solutions that could guide future work on this research field. Firstly it's important to notice that the low significance value for many of the situations analyzed could be due to the small number of samples used for the experiments and / or the experimental design itself. For a master project like this one, it's rather difficult to achieve a big enough group of subjects due to time restrictions. For the next steps of this project we are working with bigger groups and hope that would solve this issue.

About the experimental design, some points are worth mentioning. For starters, the user-customization process for the mapping scheme should be the clearest, simplest possible one. Even though we tried to achieve this, many subjects have had trouble to understand what they were controlling and how the mapping process occurs. With that in mind, a more straightforward approach should be investigated. As an example, we could use a discrete setup: instead of continuously adjusting faders to setup the mapping, the subject could simply select which feature should be mapped to which sound parameter and if this mapping should be positive or negative.

In terms of system design, we believe that the spatial filtering of the EEG signal could be further improved by using a learning phase. The system could automatically adjust each signal's spatial filter in order to maximize the variation of signal power when certain tasks are performed (e.g. maximize alpha power increase when closing eyes). This could reduce the influence of imprecise electrode positioning and the low spatial resolution of the Emotiv EPOC neuroheadset.

7.2 – Conclusions

The use of advanced sonification techniques on an auditory neurofeedback scenario has not yet been deeply explored. There is certainly a great range of research opportunities and challenges in the field and promising directions are constantly being discovered. We consider this work to be one of these seeds and also a partial success, since one of the hypotheses has been confirmed by the acquired experimental data. We also hope that this can serve as an inspiration for research to come, and that our positive results can be replicated by others.

The question of customizable mappings is left partially open and as discussed in section 7.1, we believe that a different system and experimental design could solve the problem. It's important to notice how relevant this question is. The user-customizable parameterization means that the user controls how the system works and how he or she wants to perceive his/her own state. Imagining a future scenario where auditory neurofeedback is somewhat part of society, it's really important to give the user the freedom of this choice.

References:

- [1] R. S. Huang, C. J. Kuo, L. L. Tsai, and O. T. C. Chen, "EEG pattern recognition - arousal states detection and classification," in Proc. IEEE Conf. Neural Networks, vol. 2, Jun. 1996, pp. 641–646
- [2] Schnitzlein, H. N. (1999). *The Human Brain: An Introduction To Its Functional Anatomy*.
- [3] Pravdich-Neminsky, V. V. (1913). Ein Versuch der Registrierung der elektrischen Gehirnerscheinungen. *Zbl Physiol*, 27, 951-960.
- [4] Millet, D. (2002). The Origins of EEG. In 7th Annual Meeting of the International Society for the History of the Neurosciences (ISHN).
- [5] Núñez, B., & Manuel, I. (2011). EEG artifact detection.
- [6] Hermann, T., Hunt, A., Neuhoff, J. G. (2011). *The Sonification Handbook*, chapter 1, pages 1–6. Logos Verlag.
- [7] "Neurosky," www.neurosky.com, 31/05/2013.
- [8] "Neuroelectrics," www.neuroelectrics.com, 31/05/2013.
- [9] "Emotive," www.emotiv.com, accessed: 30/03/2013.
- [10] "MindMedia Nexus," www.mindmedia.nl, 31/05/2013.
- [11] E. Adrian and B. Matthews, "The Berger rhythm: potential changes from the occipital lobes in man," *Brain*, vol. 57, no. 1, pp. 355–385, Jan. 1934.
- [12] Glen, J. (2010). Use of audio signals derived from electroencephalographic recordings as a novel 'depth of anaesthesia' monitor. *Medical hypotheses*, 75(6), 547-549.
- [13] Miranda, E. R., & Brouse, A. (2005). Interfacing the brain directly with musical systems: on developing systems for making music with brain signals. *Leonardo*, 38(4), 331-336.

- [14] Arslan, B., Brouse, A., Castet, J., Filatriau, J. J., Lehembre, R., Noirhomme, Q., & Simon, C. (2005). Biologically-driven musical instrument. In Proceedings of the Summer Workshop on Multimodal Interfaces (eNTERFACE'05).
- [15] Evans, J. R., & Abarbanel, A. (Eds.). (1999). Introduction to quantitative EEG and neurofeedback. Elsevier.
- [16] "Mathworks", www.mathworks.com (31/05/2013)
- [17] "OpenSoundControl.org", www.opensoundcontrol.org (31/05/2013)
- [18] "Low resolution Brain Electromagnetic Tomography: A new method for localizing electrical activity in the brain" R. D. Pascual-Marqui, in International Journal of Psychophysiology, 1994, pp. 49-65
- [19] Lang, P. J. (1980). Behavioral treatment and bio-behavioral assessment: Computer applications.
- [20] J. B. Sidowski, J. H. Johnson, & T. A. Williams (Eds.), Technology in mental health care delivery systems (pp. 119-137). Norwood, NJ: Ablex.
- [21] A. Valjamae et. al., A Review Of Real-Time EEG Sonification Research. In Proceedings of The 19th International Conference on Auditory Display (ICAD-2013)